

Table S1. Sampling locations of Littorinidae reported in this study.

Subfamily to species	taxon	Localily	Coordinates	
			Latitude	Longitude
Laevilitorininae				
<i>Laevilacunaria</i>	<i>L. antarctica</i>	Esperanza Bay	-63.375819	-56.988351
		Fildes Bay	-62.214258	-58.915544
		Cockburn Island	-64.185902	-56.849553
		South Orkney	-60.65646	-45.57807
		South Georgia	-54.16385	-36.69373
	<i>L. pumilio</i>	Crozet island	-46.41364	51.86616
		Kerguelen Island	-49.35313	70.218303
	<i>L. bennetti</i>	Esperanza Bay	-63.375819	-56.988351
		Yelcho Station	-64.866203	-63.589664
	<i>L. cf bennetti</i>	South Georgia	-54.28345	-36.49690
<i>Laevilitorina</i>	<i>L. antarctica</i>	Avian Island	-67.766009	-68.878253
		Deception Island	-62.970317	-60.498117
	<i>L. claviformis</i>	Deception Island	-62.970317	-60.498117
	<i>L.umbilicata</i>	Island	-62.970317	-60.498117
	<i>L. caliginosa</i>	Puerto Williams	-54.936594	-67.688353
	<i>L. fueguina</i>	Chabunco beach	-52.989559	-70.812574
		Porvenir	-53.314868	-70.459373
	<i>L. hicana</i>	Horn Island	-55.967545	-67.219303
	<i>L. latior</i>	Port Stanley	-51.700536	-57.780469
	<i>L. magellanica</i>	Chabunco beach	-52.989559	-70.812574
	<i>L. pepita</i>	Chabunco beach	-52.989559	-70.812574
		Tierra del Fuego	-52.885401	-70.248368
	<i>L. venusta</i>	Crozet island	-46.41364	51.86616
		Fildes Bay	-62.214258	-58.915544
		Kerguelen Island	-49.35313	70.218303
	<i>L. wandelensis</i>	Fildes Bay	-62.214258	-58.915544
Lacuninae		Kerguelen		
<i>Pellilitorina</i>	<i>P. setosa</i>	Island	-49.35313	70.218303
	<i>P. pellita</i>	Fildes Bay	-62.214258	-58.915544
<i>Risellopsis</i>	<i>R. varia</i>	New Zealand	-43.564626	172.758755

Table S2. Forward (F) and reverse (R) primers used for the amplification of four genes and gene-specific annealing temperatures (T_m) used in Polymerase Chain Reaction.

Gene	Sequence 5'-3'	Reference	T _m (°C)
COI			
LCO1490 (F)	GGT CAA CAA ATC ATA AAG ATA TTG G	Folmer et al. (1994)	50.5
HCO2198 (R)	TTA ACT TCA GGG TGA CCA AAA AAT CA	Williams et al. (2003)	
12S			
12SALint (F)	ACT AGG ATT AGA TAC CCT ACT ATT C	Williams et al. (2003)	54.2
12SAHint (R)	CGA GRG TGA CGG GCG ATG TGT GCA	Williams et al. (2003)	
16S			
16Sar (F)	CGCCTGTTTATCAAAAACAT	Simon et al. (1991)	48
16Sbr (R)	CCGGTCTGAACTCAGATCACGT	Simon et al. (1991)	
28S			
LSU5 (F)	TAG GTC GAC CCG CTG AAY TTA AGC A	Littlewood et al. (2000)	52.5
LSU1600 (R)	AGC GCC ATC CAT TTT CAG G	Williams et al. (2003)	

Table S2. GenBank accession numbers for four markers for Littorinidae species used in the present study

Subfamily to species	Genus	taxon	COI	12S	28S	16S
Laevilitorininae						
	<i>Laevilacunaria</i>	<i>L. antarctica</i> _EB1	PP986835	PP988552	PP985559	PP987851
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _EB2	PP986836	PP988550	PP985560	
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _FI	PP986837	PP988555	PP985561	PP987850
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _CI2	PP986838	PP988556	PP985562	
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _CI3	PP986839	PP988557	PP985563	
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _SO1	PP986842	PP988553	PP985564	
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _SO2	PP986840	PP988554	PP985565	
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _SO3	PP986841	PP988551	PP985566	
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _SG1	PP986829	PP988543	PP985573	PP987852
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _SG2	PP986828	PP988544	PP985574	
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _SG3	PP986830	PP988546	PP985572	PP987848
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _SG4	PP986831	PP988547	PP985575	PP987849
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _SG5	PP986826	PP988548	PP985571	
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _SG6	PP986827	PP988549	PP985570	
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _SG7	PP986834	PP988541	PP985569	
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _SG8	PP986833	PP988542	PP985567	
		<i>L. antarctica</i> _SG10	PP986832	PP988545	PP985568	
		<i>L. pumilio</i> _CZ	PP986843	PP988558	PP985576	PP987853
		<i>L. pumilio</i> _CZ2	PP986845	PP988559	PP985577	PP987855
		<i>L. pumilio</i> _CZ3	PP986844	PP988560	PP985578	PP987856
		<i>L. pumilio</i> _CZ4	PP986846	PP988561	PP985579	PP987854

	<i>L. bennetti_EB1</i>	PP986874	PP988534	PP985526	
	<i>L. bennetti_EB3</i>	PP986875	PP988533	PP985529	
	<i>L. bennetti_EB4</i>	PP986876	PP988532	PP985528	PP987841
	<i>L. bennetti_EB5</i>	PP986881	PP988531	PP985527	
	<i>L. bennetti_YB1</i>	PP986877	PP988530	PP985524	PP987843
	<i>L. bennetti_YB2</i>	PP986879	PP988529	PP985525	PP987842
	<i>L. bennetti_YB3</i>	PP986878	PP988527	PP985530	
	<i>L. bennetti_YB4</i>	PP986880	PP988528	PP985531	
	<i>L. cf bennetti_SG1</i>	PP986884	PP988535	PP985532	PP987845
	<i>L. cf bennetti_SG2</i>	PP986882	PP988536	PP985533	
	<i>L. cf bennetti_SG3</i>	PP986885	PP988537	PP985536	PP987846
	<i>L. cf bennetti_SG4</i>	PP986886	PP988538	PP985535	
	<i>L. cf bennetti_SG5</i>	PP986883	PP988539	PP985534	PP987847
<i>Laevilitorina</i>	<i>L. antarctica_AV1</i>	PP986847	PP988500	PP985543	
	<i>L. antarctica_AV4</i>	PP986852	PP988501	PP985542	
	<i>L. claviformis_DI2</i>	PP986851	PP988502	PP985541	PP987832
	<i>L. claviformis_DI3</i>	PP986849	PP988503	PP985540	
	<i>L. claviformis_DI4</i>	PP986850	PP988504	PP985538	
	<i>L. umbilicata_DI2</i>	PP986848	PP988505	PP985539	PP987833
	<i>L. caliginosa_WI04</i>	PP986867	PP988518	PP985516	PP987834
	<i>L. caliginosa_WI07</i>	PP986865	PP988520	PP985517	
	<i>L. caliginosa_WI08</i>	PP986866	PP988519	PP985518	PP987835
	<i>L. fueguina_CH03</i>	PP986853	PP988508	PP985552	PP987822
	<i>L. fueguina_CH04</i>	PP986854	PP988506	PP985550	PP987823
	<i>L. fueguina_PO08</i>	PP986855	PP988507	PP985551	PP987824
	<i>L. hicana_HI03</i>	PP986871	PP988526	PP985519	PP987838
	<i>L. hicana_HI13</i>	PP986872	PP988524	PP985520	PP987840
	<i>L. hicana_HI15</i>	PP986873	PP988525	PP985521	PP987839
	<i>L. latior_FA01</i>	PP986870	PP988523	PP985556	PP987836
	<i>L. latior_FA05</i>	PP986868	PP988521	PP985557	PP987837
	<i>L. latior_FA06</i>	PP986869	PP988522	PP985558	
	<i>L. magellanica_CH21</i>	PP986856	PP988508	PP985544	PP987825
	<i>L. magellanica_CH22</i>	PP986857	PP988506	PP985545	
	<i>L. magellanica_CH24</i>	PP986858	PP988507	PP985546	PP987826
	<i>L. pepita_CH07</i>	PP986859	PP988512	PP985547	PP987827
	<i>L. pepita_TR2</i>	PP986861	PP988513	PP985548	PP987828
	<i>L. pepita_TR5</i>	PP986860	PP988514	PP985549	PP987829
	<i>L. venusta_CZ4</i>	PP986862	PP988517	PP985553	
	<i>L. venusta_FI</i>	PP986864	PP988515	PP985555	PP987830
	<i>L. venusta_KE1</i>	PP986863	PP988516	PP985554	PP987831
	<i>L. wandelensis_FI</i>		PP988540	PP985537	PP987844
Lacuninae					
	<i>Pellilitorina</i>				
	<i>P. setosa_KER1</i>	PP986823	PP988499	PP985515	PP987857
	<i>P. setosa_KER2</i>	PP986824		PP985514	
	<i>P. pellita_FI</i>	PP986825		PP985513	

<i>Risellopsis</i>	<i>R. varia_NZ1</i>	PP986821	PP985522
	<i>R. varia_NZ5</i>	PP986822	PP985523

Table S3. List of gene-specific Nucleotide Substitution Models chosen by PartitionFinder

Gene	Best Model
COI	
codon position 1	GTR+I+G
codon position 2	GTR+G
codon position 3	GTR+I+G
12S	GTR+I+G
16S	GTR+I+G
28S	GTR+I+G

Table S4. BioGeoBEARS model comparison for ancestral range reconstruction in Laevilitorininae.

Model	<i>K</i>	LnL	<i>d</i>	<i>e</i>	<i>j</i>	AIC	AICc
DEC	2	-28.49	0.008	<0.00001	0	60.98	62.071
DEC+J	3	-24.82	0.005	<0.00001	0.15	55.64	58.04
DIVALIKE	2	-28.85	0.009	<0.00001	0	61.7	62.791
DIVALIKE+J	3	-25.89	0.007	<0.00001	0.085	57.78	60.18
BAYAREALIKE	2	-39.5	0.015	0.04	0	83	84.091
BAYAREALIKE+J	3	-26.91	0.003	<0.00001	0.14	59.82	62.22

SI Figure 1: Bayesian tree of maximum cladistic credibility of the relationships among Littorinidae based on 12S gene. Bayesian posterior probability (PP) and maximum likelihood bootstrap (ML) values are shown above and under the nodes.

SI Figure 2: Bayesian tree of maximum cladistic credibility of the relationships among Littorinidae based on COI gene. Bayesian posterior probability (PP) and maximum likelihood bootstrap (ML) values are shown above and under the nodes.

SI Figure 3: Bayesian tree of maximum cladistic credibility of the relationships among Littorinidae based on 28S gene. Bayesian posterior probability (PP) and maximum likelihood bootstrap (ML) values are shown above and under the nodes.

SI Figure 4: Time-calibrated phylogeny inferred from the concatenated dataset using BEAST2 under a strict molecular clock and Yule tree prior. Scenario 1 retains the two secondary calibrations used in the original analysis (Scenario 0) but specifies uniform priors across the same intervals to test sensitivity to prior shape: (1) crown Laevitorininae = 56 Ma (range 66–46 Ma; after Reid et al., 2012) and (2) divergence between the SSI/AP and South Georgia clusters of *Laevilacunaria antarctica* = 1.1 Ma (range 2.0–0.55 Ma; after González-Wevar et al., 2024). Bars denote 95% HPD intervals; node labels show median ages (Ma)

SI Figure 5: Time-calibrated phylogeny inferred from the concatenated dataset in BEAST2 under a strict molecular clock and Yule tree prior. Scenario 2 retains the two secondary calibrations but applies lognormal priors with expanded ranges to assess the effect of wider calibration uncertainty: (1) crown Laevitorininae fixed at 56 Ma with range 82–37 Ma (after Reid et al., 2012), and (2) the SSI/AP–South Georgia split in *Laevilacunaria antarctica* at 1.1 Ma with range 2.9–0.2 Ma (after González-Wevar et al., 2024). Bars indicate 95% HPD intervals; node labels show median ages (Ma).

SI Figure 6: Time-calibrated phylogeny inferred from the concatenated dataset in BEAST2 under a strict molecular clock and Yule tree prior. Scenario 3 uses a single secondary calibration, retaining only the crown age of Laevitorininae = 56 Ma (range 66–46 Ma; Reid et al., 2012) and omitting the younger calibration for the *Laevilacunaria antarctica* SSI/AP–South Georgia split. Bars denote 95% HPD intervals; node labels show median ages (Ma)